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REQUIRED SUITABILITY AND QUANTITIES OF BATTERIES FOR MOBILITY USE CASES

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Abstract

The transition toward sustainable mobility is increasingly driven by the development and adoption of battery-powered technologies across land, aerial, and maritime transport systems. However, the suitability of different battery technologies varies significantly depending on the specific operational requirements of each application. This research examines the relationship between battery characteristics and mobility use cases, with the aim of identifying which battery types are best suited for different transport scenarios.

The study begins with a technical analysis of established and emerging battery chemistries, including lithium-ion variants such as NMC, NCA, and LFP, as well as newer technologies like sodium-ion and solid-state batteries. These technologies are evaluated based on key parameters such as energy density, cycle life, safety, cost, and material dependencies. In parallel, the requirements of various mobility applications are analyzed across land-based, aerial, and maritime domains, highlighting differences in range, weight constraints, operational conditions, and charging needs.

Building on this, a compatibility framework is developed to assess how well current battery technologies align with the demands of different mobility types. The findings show that no single battery technology can meet all requirements, and that trade-offs between performance, cost, and safety must be considered in each use case. In addition, the study outlines key prerequisites for large-scale adoption, including infrastructure development, supply chain stability, regulatory support, and advancements in recycling and circular economy models.

Finally, existing gaps in knowledge and implementation are identified, particularly in relation to real-world performance data, standardization, and system-level integration. The research concludes with a technological forecast and an outlook on future developments, emphasizing the need for a system-oriented approach to battery selection and deployment to support the continued growth of electric mobility.

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III List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
BMS	Battery Management System
eVTOL	Electric Vertical Takeoff and Landing aircraft
LFP	Lithium Iron Phosphate
LTO	Lithium Titanate
Li-S	Lithium-Sulfur
NCA	Nickel Cobalt Aluminum
NMC	Nickel Manganese Cobalt
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
SoC	State of Charge
V2G	Vehicle-to-Grid
SEI	Solid Electrolyte Interphase
CNT	Carbon nanotube
MOF	Metal-organic framework
Y-FTZB	Yttrium-based metal-organic framework with 2-fluoro-4-(tetrazol-5-yl) benzoate ligand
BatPaC	Battery Performance and Cost
Ro-Ro	Roll-on/Roll-off
SLBs	Second life Batteries

1 Introduction

As more countries push for greener transport, there's been a major boost in new ideas and funding for battery-powered means of transport. At the heart of this transition is the growing move toward electric vehicles across all types of transport across all segments, from passenger cars and commercial fleets to two-wheelers, aircraft, and maritime vessels. Today, batteries stand out as the leading choice for powering electric vehicles, thanks to their reliability and scalability, enabling this transformation. As of 2025, battery-powered means of transport are considered the most practical and scalable option for decarbonizing the mobility sector, which is responsible for a substantial share of global greenhouse gas emissions.

1.1 Description of the Current Situation

In the last 20 years, battery technology has come a long way, becoming more powerful, efficient, and affordable. Lithium-ion batteries, in particular, have undergone significant optimization in terms of energy density (exceeding 250Wh/kg for certain chemistries), cycle life (greater than 2000 full charge-discharge cycles in automotive applications), and cost (below 92 €/kWh at the pack level in some markets). Simultaneously, emerging technologies such as solid-state, lithium-sulfur, and sodium-ion batteries are pushing the boundaries of what is technically and economically possible. Newer batteries are being designed to fix current problems like safety concerns, rare materials, and weight issues while enabling applications that were previously unfeasible.

Because batteries are a key piece in global tech and trade strategies. Policy is a major determinant of the pace and direction of battery-powered mobility. The production, sourcing, and recycling of battery materials such as lithium, cobalt, nickel, manganese, and graphite have become key geopolitical considerations. Many countries now see making their batteries and controlling supply chains as a top priority. Consequently, the demand for energy-dense, safe, long-lasting, and cost-effective batteries is surging, with global battery capacity expected to exceed multiple TWh annually already in few years to support electric mobility alone.

1.2 Research Objective

This research text looks at which types of batteries are suitable for different mobility needs. The main goal is to understand how the technical features of each battery type, like how much energy they store, how long they last, or how expensive they are, match up with the needs of different transport types. Specifically, the research focuses on how these batteries might be used in land vehicles (like passenger cars and trucks), aerial systems (like drones), and

maritime applications (like ships or ferries). Each of these has its own unique challenges, so not every battery fits every case. The study aims to figure out which battery chemistries make sense for which situations, based on real-world requirements.

Another part of the goal is to estimate how many batteries might be needed in the future, depending on how fast electric mobility grows. It also considers which technologies might need more development and where current options are still lacking. This includes topics like charging time, raw material supply, or thermal behavior. The research also touches briefly on the potential of newer technologies and how they might influence mobility later.

1.3 Methodology

The research follows a step-by-step approach. First, different battery technologies are described based on their chemistry and structure. This includes technical specifications like energy density (Wh/kg), charging behavior, cost per kWh, safety, and durability. The aim here is to build a clear picture of what each battery can and cannot do.

In the next step, the study looks at various types of mobility applications. These are grouped into three categories: land-based (cars, trucks, buses), aerial (e.g. drones, air taxis), and maritime (like ferries or boats). Each category has different operating conditions, some need long range, some face size or weight restrictions, and others operate in tough environments like heat, cold, or humidity.

Finally, the last part of the method connects these two parts: battery technologies and transport requirements. The idea is to see where there's a good match and where there are gaps. The findings are based on technical data and logical reasoning, rather than on market trends or brand names. That helps keep the analysis focused and objective.

1.4 Structure

This research text is structured into chapters that build upon each other.

- Chapter 1 introduces the topic, outlines the current state of battery-powered mobility, defines the research objective, and explains the methodological approach.
- Chapter 2 provides a technical overview of relevant battery types. It begins with established lithium-ion chemistries such as NMC, NCA, LFP, and LTO, followed by emerging technologies including sodium-ion, solid-state, lithium-

sulfur, flow, and zinc-air batteries. Each type is described with regard to its technical characteristics, areas of application, and limitations.

- Chapter 3 turns to the application side. It distinguishes between land-based, aerial, and maritime mobility and describes the specific requirements of each segment, without yet assigning specific battery types.
- Chapter 4 brings together the insights from the previous chapters to develop a compatibility framework. The aim is to assess which battery technologies appear suitable for which applications, where limitations exist, and which interdependencies need to be considered.
- Chapter 5 examines the prerequisites for the broader adoption of battery-powered mobility. This includes infrastructure, economic feasibility, raw material availability, standardization, regulatory conditions, and public acceptance.
- Chapter 6 identifies existing gaps in knowledge and systemic challenges when evaluating the suitability of batteries for mobility applications. The thesis concludes with a summary and an outlook on further areas of investigation.
- Chapter 7 provides a technological forecast, summarizing projected advancements in battery chemistry, cell architecture, manufacturing techniques, and energy management systems. It outlines how these trends are expected to influence future mobility solutions.
- Chapter 8 translates the forecast into use-case-specific outlooks across land-based, aerial, and maritime transport. It also discusses cross-sector integration, the role of policy frameworks, and systemic enablers necessary for large-scale deployment.
- Chapter 9 concludes the research text by summarizing key findings, revisiting the research objectives, and offering a final reflection on future research opportunities and industrial implications.

2 Battery Types

Batteries are at the heart of electric mobility, providing the energy storage needed to operate vehicles without relying on fossil fuels. Over the past two decades, significant advancements in battery chemistry, cost-efficiency, energy density, and safety have enabled broader adoption of electric transport systems. However, the wide range of requirements in different mobility applications, such as energy demand, space limitations, cost sensitivity, and operational conditions, means that no single battery type is universally suitable. This chapter provides an overview of the most important battery types used in or considered for mobility, starting with commercially established lithium-ion chemistries and progressing toward emerging and experimental alternatives.

2.1 Lithium-Ion Batteries

Lithium-ion batteries are currently the most widespread energy storage technology in electric mobility. Their success is mainly due to a strong combination of energy density, cycle life, efficiency, and decreasing production costs. Within the lithium-ion category, there are multiple chemistries differentiated by their cathode materials, each offering different trade-offs between performance, cost, and safety. The following figure provides an overview of key lithium-ion subtypes:

Figure 1: Comparison of the material composition of the current battery cathodes (Die Produktionskette „Batteriesystem“ und kritische Ressourcen, p. 21)

2.1.1 Nickel Manganese Cobalt (NMC)

Among lithium-ion chemistries, NMC batteries are widely used due to their balanced performance characteristics. The cathode is composed of nickel, manganese, and cobalt, and the exact ratio of these elements greatly influences the battery’s behavior. Early NMC versions like NMC 111 offered moderate energy density around 190Wh/kg (Pflöging 2021, p. 6) and were valued for their stable performance. Subsequent versions such as NMC 523 and NMC 622 increased the nickel content, raising energy density to approximately 170 to 180Wh/kg while slightly reducing cobalt usage, which helped lower material costs and address sourcing concerns. The most advanced version, NMC 811, pushes nickel content even further, achieving practical cell-level energy density up to 250-270Wh/kg. However, this comes at the cost of thermal stability and a shorter cycle life, as higher nickel levels make the battery more reactive under stress. The following table compares the discharge capacity of multiple NMC battery types:

Type of NMC	$\text{LiNi}_x\text{Mn}_y\text{Co}_z\text{O}_2$ ($x + y + z = 1$)	Discharge capacity
NMC 811	$\text{LiNi}_{0.8}\text{Mn}_{0.1}\text{Co}_{0.1}\text{O}_2$	215 mA h g ⁻¹
NMC 622	$\text{LiNi}_{0.6}\text{Mn}_{0.2}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$	198 mA h g ⁻¹
NMC 532	$\text{LiNi}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$	170 mA h g ⁻¹
NMC 442	$\text{LiNi}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{0.3}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{O}_2$	163 mA h g ⁻¹
NMC 111	$\text{LiNi}_{0.33}\text{Mn}_{0.33}\text{Co}_{0.33}\text{O}_2$	160 mA h g ⁻¹

Table 1 Specific capacity of different types of $\text{LiNi}_x\text{Mn}_y\text{Co}_z\text{O}_2$ (NMC) with varying Ni content for a voltage window of 3-4.2 V (Pflögl 2021, p. 5)

NMC batteries are generally considered reliable for a wide range of applications, particularly where range and charging speed are important. They also support fast-charging protocols, making them attractive for mainstream mobility. On the downside, the use of cobalt and nickel remains a concern due to their high cost, environmental impact, and ethical sourcing issues. Furthermore, batteries with higher nickel content tend to be less stable at elevated temperatures, requiring careful thermal management. The following table shows gravimetric and volumetric energy densities of LFP vs NMC batteries:

Battery Chemistry	Volumetric Energy Density (Wh L ⁻¹)	Gravimetric Energy Density (Wh kg ⁻¹)
LFP (LiFePO_4)	150 - 300	100 - 160
NMC ($\text{Li}(\text{NiMnCo})\text{O}_2$)	350 - 700	180 - 260

Table 2 Gravimetric and volumetric energy densities of LFP vs NMC batteries

2.1.2 Nickel Cobalt Aluminum (NCA)

NCA batteries are another high-performance lithium-ion subtype, typically used in premium electric vehicles that demand extended range and high-power output. These batteries can achieve energy densities of around 250 to

300Wh/kg (Koech et al. 2024, p. 333), which places them among the highest in commercially available chemistries. NCA batteries are also known for their long cycle life and consistent discharge behavior, especially under moderate operating conditions. The inclusion of aluminum in the cathode improves structural integrity and supports longer operational lifespans.

Despite these benefits, NCA batteries are not without their drawbacks. They remain expensive due to the continued reliance on cobalt and nickel, and like NMC batteries with high nickel content, they can become thermally unstable under high loads or poor cooling conditions. Safety measures and precise thermal control systems are therefore essential when deploying NCA in mobility. (Koech et al. 2024, p. 330)

2.1.3 Lithium Iron Phosphate (LFP)

LFP batteries offer a compelling alternative to NMC and NCA, especially in applications where safety, cost, and longevity are more critical than energy density. With specific energy values typically between 145-155Wh/kg, LFP batteries are less energy-dense but excel in thermal stability and cycle life, often exceeding 2,000 full charge-discharge cycles. Unlike NMC or NCA, LFP does not rely on cobalt or nickel, significantly reducing both material costs and supply chain risks.

One of the major strengths of LFP chemistry is its ability to operate safely under a wide range of temperatures, which makes it particularly attractive for use in shared transport systems or vehicles in hot climates. However, the lower energy density means that LFP batteries are heavier and bulkier, requiring more space to store the same amount of energy as other chemistries. This limits their use in applications where weight and space are at a premium. The following figure shows the advantages of lithium-iron phosphate batteries:

Battery	LiFePO ₄	LiCoO ₂	LiMn ₂ O ₄	Li(NiCo)O ₂
Safety	Safest	Not Stable	Acceptable	Not Stable
Environmental Concern	Most Enviro-friendly	Very Dangerous	Acceptable	Very Dangerous
Cycle Life	Best/ Excellent	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable
Power/Weight Density	Acceptable	Good	Acceptable	Best
Long Term Cost	Most Economic/ Excellent	High	Acceptable	High
Temperature Range	Excellent (-20C to 70C)	Decay Beyond (-20C to 55C)	Decay Extremely Fast over 50 C	-20C to 55C

Figure 2: Advantages of Lithium Iron Phosphate batteries (Why you should choose a LiFePO₄ battery for your Mil Grade UPS System, Luso Electronics, p.1)

The following table compares different types of Lithium-ion batteries:

Cathode material	Performance metrics	Energy density (Wh/kg)	Cost	Safety	Applications	Citations
Lithium Nickel Manganese Cobalt (NMC)	High specific energy (160-220 mAh/g), >1000 cycles, issues with cation mixing and metal	~900Wh/kg (theoretical)	Moderately high, cheaper than cobalt-rich materials	Safer than cobalt-based cathodes, good thermal stability (a balance between	EVs, portable electronics, energy storage systems	Jung et al., 2019, Tian et al., 2017, Shaib et al., 2022, Yabuchi and Ohzuku, 2003, Yoshizawa and Ohzuku, 2007, Lee et al., 2021

	dissolution			stability and specific energy)		
Lithium Nickel Cobalt Aluminum Oxide (NCA)	Long service life (>2000 cycles), high specific energy- 180-260 mAh/g, good specific power	Comparable to NMC, ~250-300Wh/kg	High (due to cobalt content)	Challenges with safety and cost, cobalt content raises safety concerns, recent advances to reduce and enhance thermal stability	EVs, energy storage systems, consumer electronics	Zhang et al., 2024, Oh et al., 2020, Shana et al., 2020
Lithium Iron Phosphate (LFP)	Long cycle life (>2000 cycles), stable voltage profile, low energy	90-160	Low	Very safe, high thermal and chemical stability	EVs, energy storage systems, stationary applic	Yuan et al., 2010, Stallard et al., 2022, Mauger and Julien, 2018, Tolgunbulak et al., 2021, Wu, 2019,

	density, high power capabili ty, lower voltage				ations , grid	Eftekhari, 2017
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Table 3: Lithium-ion batteries (Koech et al. 2024, p. 333)

The following figure compares LFP and NMC batteries:

Figure 3: LFP vs NMC (LFP or NMC? Which Is Better For You?, Olivia Zhang, p.1)

2.1.4 Lithium Titanate (LTO)

LTO batteries are a unique subtype of lithium-ion technology, distinguished by their use of lithium titanate in the anode. This substitution leads to exceptional safety, ultra-fast charging times, and extremely high cycle life, often exceeding 5000 cycles (Takami et al. 2013, p. 5). LTO batteries also perform well under both very high and very low temperatures, making them suitable for harsh environments or heavy-duty applications.

However, these benefits come at a significant cost to energy density. With specific energy values in the range of only 70 to 90Wh/kg, LTO batteries are not efficient in terms of energy-to-weight or energy-to-volume ratio. This makes them impractical for most passenger mobility applications, although they may

still be suitable for industrial or commercial fleets where fast turnaround and safety are prioritized over range.

2.2 Emerging Technologies

Beyond conventional lithium-ion chemistries, several battery technologies are currently under development or in early-stage commercialization. These are often referred to as "emerging technologies" because they aim to solve limitations associated with existing systems, such as material cost, environmental impact, or safety risks, while maintaining or improving energy and power performance.

2.2.1 Sodium-Ion Batteries

Sodium-ion batteries replace lithium with sodium, a much more abundant and widely available element. While their specific energy typically ranges between 100-160Wh/kg, lower than that of lithium-ion, they are still considered viable for applications that are less demanding in terms of energy density. One of the main advantages of sodium-ion batteries is their potential for lower production costs due to inexpensive raw materials. They also exhibit good thermal stability and are less sensitive to overcharging and overheating. (Bhutia et al. 2024, p. 3)

However, sodium-ion technology is still under development, and current prototypes often suffer from limited cycle life and relatively poor efficiency. While promising, they are not yet ready for large-scale mobility deployment but could play a major role in the future, especially in public transport or short-range logistics.

Figure 4: Sodium ion vs. Lithium ion Batteries (Umfeldbericht zu Natrium-Ionen-Batterien 2023, p. 8)

2.2.2 Solid-State Batteries

Solid-state batteries represent one of the most anticipated advancements in energy storage. Instead of using liquid electrolytes, they employ solid electrolytes that reduce the risk of leakage, thermal runaway, and flammability. These batteries are expected to deliver significantly higher energy densities up to 300 or even 400Wh/kg, while offering better safety and potentially longer lifespans. (Koech et al. 2024, p. 328)

Despite these advantages, solid-state batteries remain expensive and technologically challenging to produce. Issues such as solid electrolyte interface resistance, mechanical stress, and limited current densities still need to be resolved before mass production is feasible. Nevertheless, they are widely regarded as the future of high-performance mobility, particularly in aviation and premium vehicle segments. The follow figure shows the structure of a all solid state battery:

Figure 5: All solid state battery (Experimental research and design of solid state battery, p. 207)

2.3 Further Technologies

In addition to the emerging technologies, there are several other battery systems that are either in the research stage or being used in niche mobility and infrastructure applications. These technologies may not yet be ready for mainstream transport but could become relevant as energy systems evolve.

2.3.1 Lithium-Sulfur Batteries

Lithium sulfur batteries have a very high theoretical energy density over 600Wh/kg (Zhou et al. 2022, p. 312), due to the lightweight nature of sulfur. This makes them especially attractive for use in weight-sensitive applications such as drones or aircraft. Moreover, sulfur is both abundant and environmentally friendly, offering a potential alternative to cobalt- or nickel-heavy chemistries.

Lithium sulfur batteries face significant challenges with cycle life and degradation, which currently limit their commercial viability. Ongoing research aims to address these issues to make lithium-sulfur a viable solution for specific applications in the future.

2.3.2 Flow Batteries

Flow batteries store energy in two separate liquid electrolyte tanks and allow independent scaling of power and capacity. Their design is ideal for stationary applications or semi-mobile uses, such as charging infrastructure or maritime support systems. They typically offer very long operational lifespans, often exceeding 270000 charge/discharge cycles. (Alotto et al. 2014, p. 332), and are known for excellent durability.

Due to their large size and complex design, flow batteries are not well suited for mobile vehicles. However, in environments where weight is less critical and consistent power is needed such as ports or ferry systems they offer interesting possibilities for long-term use.

2.3.3 Zinc-Air Batteries

Zinc-air batteries use atmospheric oxygen as a reactant, which reduces the internal weight and simplifies the design. They are relatively cheap and environmentally friendly, and their theoretical energy density is quite high (Zhong et al. 2019, p. 1). At present, their rechargeability is limited, and performance can be affected by humidity and air purity. Still, zinc-air systems are being considered for light-duty transport, backup systems, and low-power maritime applications where cost and sustainability are top priorities.

2.4 Conclusion

This chapter has reviewed a wide range of battery technologies relevant to electric mobility. Starting from well-established lithium-ion chemistries to promising new alternatives like sodium-ion and solid-state, each battery type was discussed in terms of its technical capabilities, limitations, and application potential. While lithium-ion batteries remain the dominant force today, the

growing need for safer, cheaper, and more sustainable solutions is driving innovation in all directions. The suitability of these batteries will depend not only on their technical properties but also on how well they align with the diverse and evolving needs of future mobility systems.

3 Mobility Types

The rise of electric mobility spans across a wide variety of transport categories, each with its own technical, operational, and environmental demands. Batteries play a crucial role in meeting these demands, but before determining which technologies are best suited for which vehicle types, it is essential to understand the specific requirements of each category. This chapter divides mobility into three main segments land-based, aerial, and maritime and outlines the functional characteristics that define battery usage in these areas. The focus here is solely on the nature of these transport systems and the challenges they pose in terms of energy demand, size, weight, and environment.

3.1 Land-Based Mobility

Land-based mobility forms the largest and most mature segment in the electric vehicle space. It includes a wide range of vehicle types, each serving different functions and operating under varying conditions.

3.1.1 Passenger cars

Passenger cars are perhaps the most visible form of electric mobility. Their technical requirements vary depending on size and class, but in general, they require moderate to high range, often between 300 to 600 kilometers per charge. Weight and available installation space for batteries are constrained by the vehicle's design, especially in compact models. Efficient energy usage, low maintenance, and short charging times are critical, particularly in urban environments where vehicles are often used daily.

Buses, especially in public transport systems, operate on predictable routes with planned stops, which allows for charging during layovers. However, they carry heavy loads and must be capable of frequent acceleration and braking, which increases energy consumption. Buses also demand high reliability and robustness, as they operate across different weather and temperature conditions. The available space under the floor or on the roof gives some flexibility for battery integration, but weight still affects energy efficiency and passenger capacity. (Ntombela et al. 2023, p. 9). The following figure shows the comparison of desired driving range and EV model offering:

Figure 6: Comparison of desired driving range and EV model offering (Heiner Heimes, Achim Kampker, Wolfgang Bernhart, Isaac Chan, p. 49)

3.1.2 Two- and three-wheelers

Two- and three-wheelers, such as scooters and rickshaws, are widely used in urban and semi-urban areas, especially in regions with high population density. These vehicles have limited space for battery installation and typically require short-range capabilities, usually around 50 to 150 kilometers. Their energy needs are lower, but frequent starts and stops demand batteries that can deliver quick bursts of power without compromising efficiency. (Hossain et al. 2023, p. 6)

3.1.3 Conclusion

Overall, land-based mobility applications show the most diversity in terms of operational profiles. Energy consumption patterns, available battery space, and acceptable charging times vary significantly between vehicle classes, making it clear that no universal battery solution can serve all these needs equally well.

3.2 Aerial Mobility

Aerial mobility is still in its early stages of electrification but is rapidly gaining interest due to its potential for short-distance, point-to-point transportation and lower emissions. This category includes systems such as drones, eVTOLs (electric vertical takeoff and landing aircraft), and other prototype air vehicles. (Zhang et al. 2022, p. 1). The following figure shows different types of EVTOLs:

eVTOL (Electric Vertical Take-Off And Landing)

eVTOLs are primarily developed for UAM (Urban Air Mobility), though some also target RAM (Regional Air Mobility). Most battery specifications remain undisclosed. Market-ready models rely on high-end lithium-ion batteries, while designs in development feature innovative chemistries like solid-state, lithium-sulfur, or metal-air. Under investments pressure, the choice of chemistry is driven by the aircraft launch and certification timeline.

AIRCRAFT	VoloCity - Volocopter	EH216-S - EHang	S4 - Joby Aviation	Midnight - Archer	Prosperity 1 - Autoflight	AE200 X01 - Aerofugia	VX4 - Vertical Aerospace
MAX TAKE-OFF MASS	1000 kg	620 kg	2400 kg	3175 kg	1500 kg	-	-
# PASSENGERS	1+1 pilot	2 (autonomous)	4+1 pilot	4 +1 pilot	4 (autonomous)	4+1 pilot	4 + 1 pilot
RANGE	20 km	35 km	161 km	32-80 km	250 km	-	161 km
POWER SUPPLY	Battery Electric	Battery Electric	Battery Electric				
CHARGING SYSTEM	Battery Swap	-	-	Fast Charge	-	-	Fast Charge
BATTERY	Lithium-ion	17 kWh	Lithium-ion 235 Wh/kg (pack level)	Lithium-ion (Molicel) 142 kWh	160 kWh	-	Lithium-ion (Molicel)
FIRST FLIGHT	2021	2018	2018	2023	2022	2023	2023
ENTRY INTO SERVICE (ANNOUNCED)	2025	2023	2025	2025	2026	2026	2027

Figure 7: Electric vertical take-off and landing (Battery Report 2024, p. 178)

3.2.1 Drones

Drones, especially those used for delivery or surveying, require light-weight energy solutions that allow for vertical lift and agile maneuverability. These systems often operate within ranges of 10 to 50 kilometers and must be able to take off and land multiple times within a short duration. High energy density and low weight are crucial to maximize flight time without compromising payload capacity. Because of the altitude and dynamic movement, battery systems must also remain thermally stable and vibration-resistant. Depending on the payload and mission duration, typical battery capacities range from 1 to 5kWh, with specific energy targets of around 200 to 300Wh/kg. Air taxis and eVTOL prototypes are an emerging class of passenger transport vehicles intended for urban use. These vehicles aim to transport two to five people over relatively short distances up to 100 kilometers within and between city areas. The key requirements for this segment are high power output during takeoff and landing, low total system weight, and short turnaround times between flights. Safety and redundancy are critical, and any failure in power supply could lead to dangerous outcomes, so reliability under all operating conditions is non-negotiable. As these aircraft are expected to operate in regulated airspace, their energy systems must meet strict certification requirements. eVTOL systems typically require battery packs ranging from 60 to 150kWh, with specific energy needs often exceeding 300 Wh/kg to achieve the necessary range and performance. (Zhang et al. 2022, p. 3)

3.2.2 eVTOL

Air taxis and eVTOL prototypes are an emerging class of passenger transport vehicles intended for urban use. These vehicles aim to transport two to five people over relatively short distances up to 100 kilometers within and between city areas. The key requirements for this segment are high power output during takeoff and landing, low total system weight, and short turnaround times between flights. Safety and redundancy are critical, and any failure in power supply could lead to dangerous outcomes, so reliability under all operating conditions is non-negotiable. As these aircraft are expected to operate in regulated airspace, their energy systems must meet strict certification requirements. eVTOL systems typically require battery packs ranging from 60 to 150kWh, with specific energy needs often exceeding 300Wh/kg to achieve the necessary range and performance. (Zhang et al. 2022, p. 4)

3.2.3 Airships

Airships and hybrid platforms designed for surveillance, communication, or cargo transport offer longer flight durations and larger payloads. These systems can tolerate slightly more weight but still require optimized energy systems to enable long-range operation, often beyond 200 kilometers. Environmental factors such as altitude, temperature shifts, and atmospheric pressure fluctuations influence battery performance significantly in this domain. Depending on the mission profile, airship battery systems typically range from 100 to 500kWh, and must maintain stable performance over long durations in low-pressure conditions. In general, aerial mobility places an extremely high emphasis on energy-to-weight ratio and safety. Any energy system deployed in this category must not only be efficient but also extremely compact and resistant to harsh environmental conditions. (Zhang et al. 2022, p. 7)

3.2.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, electrification is poised to transform aerial mobility by addressing the stringent demands of power density, weight, safety, and environmental resilience across a diverse set of platforms from agile delivery drones and urban eVTOL air taxis to long-endurance airships. Each application imposes unique energy-system requirements, whether it's maximizing flight time with ultra-light batteries in drones, ensuring rapid high-power output and redundancy in eVTOLs, or sustaining hundreds of kilowatt-hours under variable atmospheric conditions for airships. As battery technology continues to advance toward higher specific energies and greater reliability, these electric air vehicles will become increasingly viable, unlocking cleaner, more efficient point-to-point transport that can reshape both urban and long-range aerial operations.

3.3 Maritime Mobility

Maritime transport includes a diverse range of vehicles, from small ferries and patrol boats to large ships and support systems at ports. While electrification in this field is less developed than in land transport, several use cases are gaining momentum. (Aksöz et al. 2025, p. 1)

3.3.1 Ferries

Ferries, especially those operating on short coastal or inland routes, are well suited for electrification due to their repetitive, predictable schedules. These vessels often travel between fixed points several times per day, allowing for controlled charging intervals. They typically require moderate energy capacity, but because weight is less of an issue on water, they can accommodate larger battery systems. Battery capacities for electric ferries usually range from 500kWh to over 3MWh, depending on size and route length. However, corrosion, salt exposure, and water ingress are serious concerns, so battery systems must be designed to handle marine conditions reliably. (Aksöz et al. 2025, p. 2)

3.3.2 Ships

Larger ships, including cargo vessels and support craft, have much higher energy requirements and often operate for long periods without access to shore-based charging infrastructure. While full electrification of such ships is still in early development, hybrid systems and partial electrification are becoming more common, especially for auxiliary systems. Energy requirements vary widely but can exceed 10MWh for fully electric or hybrid cargo vessels. The space available on ships is relatively generous, but thermal management and long-term durability are essential due to the extended durations and variable loads these vessels experience. (Aksöz et al. 2025, p. 3)

3.3.3 Maritime support systems

Maritime support systems such as tugboats, pilot vessels, and port-side equipment are also being electrified to reduce emissions in port areas. These systems require rapid availability, high reliability, and robustness against the elements. The operational cycles are usually short but intense, involving high bursts of power and frequent maneuvering. Battery systems typically range from 200 to 1500kWh for these applications. Maritime environments are uniquely challenging due to the presence of salt, moisture, and continuous vibrations. Battery systems used here must be sealed, temperature-controlled, and capable of withstanding long periods of idle time without degrading. Weight is

less of a constraint compared to aerial or land-based systems, allowing for more flexibility in battery size and layout. (Aksöz et al. 2025, p. 27)

3.4 Conclusion

In summary, the three mobility domains of land, air and sea each present a distinct set of design trade-offs that battery systems must address. On land, the wide range of vehicles from compact cars to heavy buses requires a careful balance among energy density, packaging constraints and rapid charging capability. In the air, whether for agile delivery drones or emerging eVTOL air taxis, strict limits on weight combined with high power demands drive the development of lighter chemistries and highly reliable architectures. At sea, larger vessel dimensions and regular ferry schedules allow for multi-megawatt-hour battery installations but introduce challenges in corrosion resistance, thermal management and endurance over long cycles.

These findings make it clear that no single battery technology can meet the needs of all transport modes. Instead, engineers and researchers must adapt cell chemistries, pack architectures and cooling strategies to the specific duty cycles and environmental conditions of each application. As electrification continues its advance on roads, in the sky and on the water, a modular, system-level approach to energy storage that fully integrates vehicle design, operational profile and charging infrastructure will be essential to realizing the promise of electric mobility.

4 Framework: Matching Battery Types to Mobility Applications

After exploring the technical characteristics of different batteries and examining the specific demands of various mobility types in previous chapters, this chapter brings both perspectives together. The aim is to develop a practical compatibility framework that illustrates how well today's battery technologies meet the requirements of land, air, and sea transportation. Rather than identifying a single "best" battery for each use case, the framework acknowledges that real-world applications involve compromises and limitations. It instead provides a well-rounded assessment based on factors like performance, safety, and ease of integration.

4.1 Land-Based Mobility

Land-based mobility includes a broad spectrum of vehicles, ranging from lightweight two-wheelers to heavy-duty commercial trucks. Each class places different demands on energy systems in terms of range, space, safety, and cost. The following figure shows the EV's range influence factors:

Figure 2. The main influence factors on EV's range (constants and variables).

Figure 8: EV's range influence factors (Varga et al. 2019, p. 4)

4.1.1 Mid-range passenger mobility

In the case of passenger vehicles, energy density and fast-charging capability are crucial. For this reason, NMC and NCA batteries are widely used in electric cars today. Their high energy density often exceeding 200Wh/kg. (Ding et al. 2019, p. 11) enables longer driving range without excessive battery mass, while their compatibility with fast-charging infrastructure supports user convenience. NMC 622 and 811, in particular, are favored for their improved range (Ding et al. 2019, p. 11), though they require more complex thermal management systems. In contrast, LFP batteries are gaining popularity in compact cars, especially for city driving, due to their excellent thermal stability, safety profile, and lower cost. Although their energy density is lower, around 90-170Wh/kg (Ding et al. 2019, p. 10), it is often sufficient for vehicles designed for daily urban use. LTO batteries, despite their fast-charging speed and very long cycle life, are rarely used in passenger vehicles due to their very low energy density, which makes them unsuitable for weight-sensitive applications unless the use case is highly specialized, such as shuttle fleets or taxis with high utilization rates.

4.1.2 Long-range transport

Long-range transport, particularly in the form of heavy-duty trucks and long-haul vehicles, places extreme demands on battery systems due to the need for extended driving ranges, often exceeding 500 kilometers per charge. In this context, energy density becomes the critical parameter, as heavier batteries reduce payload capacity and operational efficiency. Chemistries like NMC 622 and NMC 811, offering up to 270Wh/kg (Ding et al. 2019, p. 13), are currently among the most viable options, combining high storage capacity with fast-charging capability. However, their use requires advanced thermal management and entails reliance on materials like nickel and cobalt, which increases both cost and supply chain vulnerability. Solid-state batteries, still under development, are expected to provide even higher energy densities above 300Wh/kg (Ding et al. 2019, p. 13), offering a future-oriented solution for reducing battery weight while extending range.

Alternative chemistries such as sodium-ion batteries, despite their lower energy density of around 120-60Wh/kg, are being explored for mid-range freight operations where cost and material availability are critical. Their improved thermal stability and reduced reliance on scarce resources position them as a practical solution for regional logistics fleets. In contrast, low-density chemistries such as LFP (90-160Wh/kg) are generally unsuitable for long-range use due to their space and weight requirements. Overall, battery selection for long-distance freight must prioritize maximum energy output per unit mass while ensuring thermal safety, economic feasibility, and infrastructure compatibility.

4.1.3 Public Transport (Electric Buses)

Electric buses in public transport typically run on fixed routes with daily distances between 100 and 250 kilometers. Because they operate in urban areas with frequent stops, starts, and traffic lights, the battery has to handle many charge and discharge cycles and support a high number of daily operations. Most electric buses today are equipped with battery packs in the range of 250 to 400kWh (Vilppo and Markkula 2015, p. 7), depending on the route profile, vehicle size, and climate conditions. LFP batteries are the most commonly used in this area because they are stable, safe, and have a long service life. Their energy density is usually between 90 and 130Wh/kg (Vilppo and Markkula 2015, p. 6), which is lower than other chemistries, but not a major disadvantage in this case. Since buses have available space on the roof or under the floor, a larger and heavier battery can be installed without affecting passenger capacity too much.

Charging usually takes place overnight in bus depots, where slower AC or mid-power DC chargers are used. This works well for most schedules. In some systems, especially with high-frequency routes or tighter schedules, opportunity charging is used. This means the bus charges during short breaks at terminal stops, often using fast chargers rated at 300kW or more (Vilppo and Markkula 2015, p. 5). In situations where the bus needs to travel longer distances or charging infrastructure is limited, NMC batteries are sometimes used instead. They can reach energy densities of up to 270Wh/kg, which helps extend range or reduce battery size, but they are more expensive and require better thermal management to operate safely. Overall, battery systems for electric buses are chosen based on long cycle life, low maintenance, thermal stability, and total cost of ownership. That is why LFP batteries remain the preferred option for most public transport fleets operating in cities. (Vilppo and Markkula 2015, p. 5) The following figure shows lithium ion batteries types and KPIs:

Li-ion battery type	Specific energy (Wh/kg)	Energy density (Wh/L)	Cost (\$/kWh)
NMC-111	180	400	145
NMC-532	220	500	130
NMC-622	260	650	100
NMC-811	280	700	90
NCA	280	750	90
LFP	185	430	80

Figure 9: Lithium ion batteries types and KPIs (Petros Ioannou and Bingtao Hu, p. 12)

4.1.4 Logistics: Light vs Heavy Load Application

Electric vehicles used for transporting goods come in many forms, from small delivery vans to large trucks. Each type has different energy needs depending

on the size of the vehicle, the weight it carries, and how far it drives in a day. Light-duty vehicles like vans and small trucks are mostly used for city deliveries and last-mile logistics (Juan et al. 2016, p. 6). They usually travel between 80 and 200 kilometers per day and need battery packs in the range of 40 to 100kWh. Since these vehicles are smaller and operate on fixed schedules, LFP batteries are a common choice. They are cheaper, thermally stable, and last longer, which is useful in stop-and-go traffic. The lower energy density, normally between 90 and 160 Wh per kg, is not a big problem here because these vehicles are not carrying very heavy loads.

Heavy-duty trucks used for regional or long-distance deliveries need much larger batteries because they often travel over 300 kilometers a day and carry heavy cargo. Battery sizes in this group can range from 400 to 1000kWh. Since battery weight affects how much the truck can carry, energy density becomes a much more important factor. NMC batteries, especially NMC 622 or 811, are more suitable here as they can reach up to 270 Wh per kg. These batteries can store more energy in a smaller space but are more expensive and need stronger cooling systems to work safely under load. Solid-state batteries are being researched as a future solution for this segment since they are expected to go beyond 300 Wh per kg while also improving safety. Sodium-ion batteries are also being tested for mid-range trucks where high energy density is not as important, and cost or material availability plays a bigger role. In the logistics sector, light-duty vehicles focus more on reliability and low cost, while heavy-duty transport needs efficient energy storage that does not eat into payload capacity. (Juan et al. 2016, p. 7)

4.1.5 Conclusion

The choice of battery really depends on what kind of vehicle is being used and what it's meant to do. For passenger cars, especially those that need to go longer distances, energy density and charging speed matter the most, which is why NMC and NCA batteries are common. For city cars, where range is not as big of a concern, LFP batteries work well because they're cheaper and safer. In long-range transport like heavy trucks, the battery has to store a lot of energy without adding too much weight, so high-density batteries like NMC 811 are often used, even though they cost more and need better cooling. Solid-state batteries might become more important here in the future. Electric buses are different because they follow fixed routes and charge at depots. That makes LFP a good fit, since it's reliable and lasts a long time. In goods transport, smaller vehicles usually use LFP because it's affordable and does the job, while larger trucks need more powerful batteries to deal with long distances and heavy loads. All in all, each type of transport has its own needs, and there's no single battery that fits everything. It's all about finding the right match for each case.

4.2 Aerial Mobility

The demands of aerial mobility are fundamentally different from ground transport. Weight is a dominant constraint, while energy delivery must be consistent and safe at altitude. These systems often operate in short bursts, such as during takeoff and landing, followed by lower-energy cruising phases. As a result, energy-to-weight ratio, power output, and thermal safety are all crucial.

4.2.1 Battery Suitability for Delivery and Survey Drones

For small drones, current NMC batteries are generally sufficient. They offer decent energy density and discharge rates suitable for short-range flights, typically under 50 km. However, the need to reduce mass has led to research into higher-density alternatives. Solid-state batteries, with their potential to exceed 300Wh/kg and enhanced thermal stability, are being closely watched as a future option. Despite their theoretical advantages, they are not yet commercially viable due to challenges in cost, manufacturing complexity, and reliability.

Chemistry	Gravimetric Energy Density (Wh/kg)	Power Density (W/kg)
Lithium titanate oxide (LTO)	60–110	1000–10,000
Lithium iron phosphate (LFP)	90–160	1000–3000
Lithium manganese iron phosphate (LMFP)	120–180	1000–3000
Lithium manganese oxide (LMO)	100–150	1000–3000
Lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide (NCA)	200–260	800–2000
Lithium nickel cobalt manganese aluminum oxide (NCMA)	200–250	800–2000
Lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxides (NMC)	150–220	800–2000
Requirement for eVTOL	240	2000

Figure 10: Comparison of current battery chemistries with eVTOL requirements (Fay et al. 2025, p. 8)

4.2.2 Energy Demands of Electric Vertical Takeoff Aircraft

Air taxis and eVTOL systems push battery requirements even further. These aircraft demand high peak power for vertical takeoff and landing, followed by stable energy output during horizontal flight. Lithium-sulfur batteries could be advantageous in this context due to their very high theoretical energy density up to 550Wh/kg. (Fay et al. 2025, p. 10) However, their extremely short cycle life and instability under repeated cycling make them impractical at this stage. NMC remains the practical choice for early-stage prototypes, but longer-term, solid-state or hybrid chemistries may become necessary to meet the demanding flight profiles and certification requirements.

Battery Chemistry	Gravimetric Energy Density (Wh/kg)	Power Density (W/kg)
Magnesium-ion (MIB)	80–120	100–300
Zinc-ion (ZIB)	50–120	30–150
Aluminum-ion (AIB)	40–220	>3000
Sodium-ion (SIB)	200	300
Lithium-sulfur (Li-S)	550	<500

Figure 11: Technical parameters of emerging battery chemistries (Fay et al. 2025, p. 10)

4.3 Maritime Mobility

Compared to land and air vehicles, maritime systems allow for more flexibility in terms of weight and volume. As such, batteries used in this sector prioritize longevity, cost efficiency, and resistance to environmental stressors like humidity, salt corrosion, and vibration. Applications range from small ferries to large ocean-going vessels and harbor-side energy systems.

4.3.1 Battery Use in Short-Route Ferries

In short-route ferries, LFP batteries are the most widely adopted. Their long cycle life, low maintenance requirements, and strong thermal stability make them ideal for regular, scheduled operations where the vessel returns to dock frequently for charging. In this setting, energy density is less of a constraint, as vessel weight does not directly impact range as it does in road vehicles.

4.3.2 Energy Storage for Large Maritime Vessels

Larger maritime vessels, such as container ships or tankers, require enormous energy storage to operate purely on battery power. Given current battery technology limitations, these vessels are more likely to use hybrid systems that combine battery storage with conventional fuels or hydrogen. Flow batteries and zinc-air systems are being researched for such use cases, particularly for auxiliary power systems or as part of port-based microgrids. Their long cycle life and high capacity make them well suited for stable, continuous energy supply though their low power density limits their use for propulsion.

4.3.3 Electrification of Port and Support Equipment

Port-based applications such as tugboats, pilot vessels, and loading systems are also increasingly electrified. Here, rapid power availability and rugged design are priorities. LFP again proves suitable, though sodium-ion systems may also enter this space once they mature, especially in applications where cost and safety are more important than high energy density.

4.3.4 Summary of Compatibility

Ultimately, the suitability of a battery for any given mobility application depends on several intertwined factors: energy density, weight, charging behavior, cost, safety, and environmental resilience. While lithium-ion batteries particularly NMC, NCA, and LFP, currently dominate, their relative advantages vary by use case. No single battery type is optimal for all vehicles, and each choice involves a trade-off between competing priorities.

Furthermore, real-world implementation requires more than just performance metrics. Considerations such as supply chain logistics, vehicle integration, thermal management, and even user behavior play a role in determining true compatibility. As battery research evolves and new chemistries are developed, the landscape will continue to shift. Flexibility in design and an iterative approach to battery selection will remain essential in meeting the dynamic needs of electric mobility.

5 Prerequisites for the Spread of Battery Technologies

While battery technologies have progressed significantly, their successful integration into the mobility sector relies not just on technical performance but on a complex set of external conditions. Factors such as infrastructure readiness, economic feasibility, regulatory support, and public acceptance can either accelerate or inhibit the adoption of new energy systems. This chapter outlines the most critical prerequisites that must be in place for battery-powered mobility to scale sustainably across land, aerial, and maritime domains.

5.1 EV Charging Infrastructure and Grid Synergy

A functioning and accessible charging infrastructure is the backbone of any widespread electric mobility system. Without it, even the most advanced battery technologies cannot be effectively deployed. In urban environments, charging must be integrated into both public and private spaces, including residential buildings, parking garages, shopping areas, and office parks. This includes a mix of regular and fast-charging stations, depending on user needs.

5.2 Commercial Fleet Charging Networks

In the context of commercial fleets buses, trucks, and taxis charging infrastructure must support high-power, multi-vehicle charging with minimal downtime. Depot charging and opportunity charging along routes must be coordinated with vehicle schedules.

5.3 Aerial and Maritime Charging Facilities

Aerial and maritime mobility introduce unique challenges. Drones and eVTOL aircraft require fast, lightweight, and compact charging systems, potentially at distributed landing zones. Maritime systems need corrosion-resistant, high-voltage equipment that can withstand port environments and rough weather.

5.4 Grid Capacity and Smart-Grid Integration

The electrical grid also plays a decisive role. As the number of electric vehicles grows, so does the demand on local grids. Sudden spikes, such as multiple trucks charging at a depot, can stress the network and cause instability. Smart grid technologies, including load balancing and vehicle-to-grid (V2G) integration, are being explored to alleviate this issue. However, the deployment of such systems remains limited and requires significant public and private investment, as well as regulatory coordination. (Yuvaraj et al. 2024, p. 5414)

5.5 Cost-Benefit Analysis and Incentive Structures

Cost remains one of the primary obstacles to battery technology adoption, especially for newer chemistries such as solid-state, lithium-sulfur, and sodium-ion batteries. Although lithium-ion battery prices have dropped significantly in the last decade, reaching levels below €140 per kWh in many cases, other systems remain too expensive for mainstream use. Many public transport operators and logistics companies operate on tight budgets, and switching to electric power often requires not only investment in vehicles but also charging infrastructure and workforce training.

Government subsidies, tax incentives, and public grants can temporarily reduce this barrier and accelerate adoption. Countries that have implemented incentive programs such as the German "Umweltbonus" or California's EV rebate have seen faster uptake of battery-powered vehicles. However, for long-term success, batteries must become economically viable without government intervention. This requires ongoing reductions in production cost through economies of scale, localized manufacturing, and improved supply chain coordination. (Petros Ioannou and Bingtao Hu, p. 12)

5.6 Raw-Material Supply Chains and Sourcing Risks

The global battery industry depends on several critical raw materials: lithium, cobalt, nickel, and manganese. Many of these are sourced from a limited number of countries, which creates vulnerability to geopolitical disruptions, export restrictions, and labor rights concerns. For example, a large share of the world's cobalt is mined in the Democratic Republic of Congo, where working conditions and environmental standards have faced international scrutiny.

To ensure reliable and ethical sourcing, supply chain transparency and diversification are essential. Some companies are investing in vertical integration, controlling both mining and battery production, while others are exploring alternative chemistries that reduce dependency on scarce elements. Sodium-ion and LFP batteries are particularly attractive in this context, as they avoid cobalt and use more abundant materials. Nonetheless, large-scale adoption requires global coordination and long-term planning to avoid future bottlenecks. (Responsible and sustainable sourcing of battery raw materials 2020, p. 26)

5.7 Standards, Protocols and Interoperability

The lack of standardization across battery systems presents another obstacle to adoption. Different manufacturers use different cell formats, communication

protocols, battery management systems (BMS), and connector types. This creates compatibility issues and increases costs for vehicle integration, maintenance, and recycling. For example, a bus from one manufacturer may not be able to use the same charger or spare parts as a model from another brand.

Establishing industry-wide standards for battery modules, interfaces, and testing procedures would simplify supply chains, facilitate second-life applications, and reduce waste. It would also enable battery swapping in commercial fleets, an idea being tested in some Asian markets where downtime is critical. While full harmonization is unlikely in the short term due to competitive interests, broader collaboration between OEMs, suppliers, and regulators will be necessary to move the industry forward. (Haghbin et al., p. 11)

5.8 Regulatory Landscape and Policy Drivers

Public policy plays a central role in enabling or delaying the spread of battery-powered mobility. Clear long-term targets, such as CO₂ emission limits, combustion engine phase-out dates, and urban access restrictions, give industry players the certainty needed to invest in new technologies. Moreover, safety regulations, environmental compliance rules, and recycling mandates define the conditions under which batteries can be manufactured, transported, used, and retired.

However, regulatory inconsistency across regions remains a challenge. A battery that meets EU safety and transport regulations may still face approval hurdles in other markets. The development of globally harmonized regulations would greatly facilitate international trade and technology transfer. In addition, governments must play an active role in financing RandD, supporting pilot projects, and reducing legal and financial risks for companies testing next-generation technologies. (Fatih Canitez 2025, p. 14)

5.9 Consumer Perception and Adoption Barriers

Technological readiness does not guarantee market acceptance. Many consumers still harbor doubts about battery durability, charging times, long-term maintenance costs, and environmental impact. Misinformation or lack of experience with electric vehicles can lead to hesitation, especially among older or rural populations. In commercial contexts, fleet operators are often skeptical of switching technologies due to perceived risks and the complexity of fleet electrification.

Building trust in battery systems requires transparency, demonstration projects, and reliable performance data. For instance, publishing real-world cycle life,

degradation patterns, and second-life potential can help reduce uncertainty. Educational campaigns and user-friendly digital tools that track battery health and suggest optimal usage practices can also increase user confidence. Social acceptance is especially important in the aerial and maritime domains, where safety and public perception play a major role in project approval. (Fatih Canitez 2025, p. 17)

5.10 Circular-Economy Models and Recycling Strategies

As battery usage grows, so does the urgency to manage them responsibly at end-of-life. Currently, most battery recycling systems are optimized for lithium-ion chemistries, and even these processes are often inefficient or economically unviable without subsidies. For newer battery types like solid-state or sodium-ion, recycling methods are still in the early stages of development.

Design for recyclability and reuse must become an integral part of battery engineering. Modular construction, standardized materials, and easier disassembly can all contribute to a more circular battery economy. Second-life applications, such as using retired EV batteries in stationary energy storage, offer additional value but require performance validation and regulatory approval. Without robust end-of-life strategies, the environmental benefits of battery-powered mobility could be offset by increased waste and resource strain. (Machín et al. 2024, p. 14)

6 Gap Analysis- Missing Information on Compatibility

Despite the growing body of knowledge surrounding battery technologies and their integration into mobility applications, several areas of uncertainty remain. These gaps are not only technical but also methodological, economic, and systemic. They hinder the ability to make confident decisions regarding which battery types are best suited to specific transport modes and prevent the development of truly optimized, long-term solutions. This chapter identifies the most relevant knowledge and implementation gaps that must be addressed to enable a seamless and scalable transition to battery-powered mobility.

6.1 Lack of Real-World Operational Data

One of the most persistent issues is the disconnect between laboratory testing and real-world usage. Most battery data, including specific energy, cycle life, and charging behavior, is gathered under controlled conditions, where variables such as ambient temperature, load patterns, and state-of-charge limits are tightly regulated. However, actual usage introduces far more variability. Urban buses may face temperature extremes, drones may experience intermittent power bursts, and trucks may remain partially charged for days before use.

These unpredictable and often mixed-use profiles impact battery degradation, thermal performance, and efficiency in poorly understood ways. Without robust and long-term field data, it is difficult to create reliable battery management systems or to choose the most appropriate chemistry for a given application. This lack of transparency also makes it harder for public and private stakeholders to assess the total cost of ownership or plan infrastructure investments. (Schreiber et al. 2025, p. 3)

6.2 Absence of Unified Testing Standards Across Sectors

Another gap lies in the inconsistent testing and qualification procedures between mobility sectors. While the automotive industry has established well-defined benchmarks for battery safety, performance, and certification, similar protocols are still underdeveloped or fragmented in maritime and aerial contexts. This creates uncertainty when attempting to evaluate cross-sector applications or when adapting a proven battery system from one transport domain to another. The following figure shows applicable scope and characteristics of the general standards for LIBs:

Standard System	Standard Name	Scope	Technical Features
ISO	ISO 6469-1 (2019) [60]	System	Battery system safety specifications
	ISO 6469-3 (2021) [61]		Electrical Safety
	ISO 6469-4 (2015) [62]		Electrical safety after crash
	ISO 12405-1 (2011) [63]	Pack and Module	Requirements for reliability and resistance to abuse for power batteries
	ISO 12405-2 (2012) [64]		Requirements for reliability and resistance to abuse for energy batteries
	ISO 12405-3 (2014) [65]		Safety requirements oriented from accidents that electric vehicles may encounter in use
	ISO 12405-4 (2018) [66]	Module and System	Basic performance tests
Standard System	Standard Name	Scope	Technical Features
IEC	IEC 62660-1 (2018) [67]	Cell	Basic performance tests
	IEC 62660-2 (2018) [68]		Reliability and abuse testing, electrical, mechanical, environmental, and other abuse tests
	IEC 62660-3 (2022) [69]		Safety requirements, including electrical, mechanical, environmental, and other safety tests
	IEC 62619 (2022) [70]	Cell, Module, and System	Safety requirements for energy storage systems
	IEC 63056 (2020) [71]		Safety requirements for energy storage systems
SAE	SAE J2464 (2021) [72]	Cell, Module, and System	Safety and abuse testing
	SAE J2929 (2013) [73]	Cell, Module, and System	Safety requirements for single cells
	SAE J2380 (2021) [74]	Cell	Vibration test
FreedomCAR	SAND2005-3123 (2005) [75]	Cell, Module, and Pack	Safety requirements and test methods
UL	UL 1642 (2020) [76]	Cell and Module	Safety requirements
	UL 2580 (2020) [77]		Safety requirements for vehicle power batteries
	UL 9540 A (2019) [78]	Cell and System	Safety requirements for energy storage systems
	UL 1973 (2022) [79]		Safety requirements for energy storage systems
GB	QC/T 743 (2006) [80]	Cell	Safety requirements and test methods
	GB/T 31485 (2015) [81]		Safety and experimental methods
	GB 31467.3 (2015) [82]	Pack and System	Safety requirements and test methods
	GB/T 36276 (2018) [83]	Cell, Module, and System	Safety requirements for energy storage systems
	GB 38031 (2020) [84]		Security requirements

Figure 12: Applicable scope and characteristics of the general standards for LIBs. (Lai et al. 2022)

For example, a battery validated for use in electric trucks may require completely different safety mechanisms for integration into a drone or ship, even if its performance profile seems similar on paper. Without harmonized standards especially in areas such as thermal stability, shock resistance, and environmental exposure comparison and transferability remain limited, which slows down innovation and multiplies development costs.

6.3 Limited Understanding of Mixed-Cycle Aging and Degradation

Battery degradation is typically modeled based on simple, repetitive usage patterns, such as full charge/discharge cycles at constant rates. However, most real-world applications involve partial charges, idle periods, regenerative braking, and irregular loads. In some cases, these complex cycles may accelerate degradation through non-linear chemical or thermal mechanisms, which are not captured in standard aging models

This is particularly critical in fleet operations and logistics, where vehicles are used intensively and unpredictably. For instance, delivery trucks might undergo dozens of short trips per day with varying loads and stop-start conditions, which place uneven stress on cells. The industry currently lacks tools that can accurately predict long-term performance under such conditions. As a result, battery sizing, warranty calculations, and replacement planning are often based on conservative estimates rather than precise forecasts (Li et al. 2024, p. 15).

6.4 Overlooked System-Level Integration Challenges

Another underexplored area is the integration of batteries into complex vehicle systems. Batteries are not standalone units; they operate in conjunction with inverters, cooling systems, thermal management components, and vehicle control units. High-energy-density chemistries, for example, often require more sophisticated cooling solutions, which in turn add weight, occupy space, and draw power.

Many compatibility assessments treat the battery in isolation, without accounting for these trade-offs. This can lead to misaligned expectations or suboptimal system designs. For example, a chemistry with excellent energy density may reduce available payload in a truck due to added cooling infrastructure. A system-level perspective is essential to identify the most efficient battery technology, not just in terms of energy per kilogram, but also considering volume, integration complexity, and impact on overall vehicle performance. (Chavan et al. 2024, p. 19)

6.5 Recycling and End-of-Life Handling Uncertainties

The lack of clarity around battery recycling and second-life usage is becoming a more serious issue, especially as emerging chemistries move closer to commercialization. While lithium-ion systems are supported by a growing recycling industry, other chemistries such as solid-state, sodium-ion, and lithium-sulfur still lack well-defined processes for safe dismantling and material recovery. (Tembo et al. 2024, p. 16).

This creates uncertainty around total environmental impact and life cycle emissions. Without proven recycling pathways, manufacturers and policymakers cannot fully assess the long-term sustainability of newer batteries. In addition, current recycling infrastructure is not always compatible with large-format cells used in trucks or maritime applications. This adds another layer of complexity to the evaluation of battery-vehicle compatibility over the full product life cycle. (Tembo et al. 2024, p. 17).

6.6 Economic Forecasting and Cost Modeling Gaps

Battery cost projections often focus on cell-level prices (€/kWh), but overlook system-level costs such as cooling, integration, software, installation, and regulatory compliance. Furthermore, many newer chemistries are still in pilot or prototype phases, making their production costs speculative and highly sensitive to scale (Knehr et al., pp. 103-104). The following figure shows list of purchased items for the cell, module, and pack.:

Component, i	Material	Cost Equation, \$/unit	Cost per unit
<u>Cell-level</u>			
Positive terminal	Aluminum	$0.08 + 2.41m_i$	Cell
Negative terminal	Copper	$0.08 + 8.64m_i$	Cell
Container	PET-Al-PP	$0.20 + 3.00m_i$	Cell
Heat conductor	Aluminum	$0.15 + 2.41m_i$	Cell
<u>Module-level</u>			
Module management system	-	$2.00 + 6.00C_{mod}$	Parallel cell group
Cell interconnect	Copper	$0.04 + 8.72m_i$	Interconnect
Interconnect panel	Polypropylene	$0.20 + 2.30m_i$	Panel
Terminals	Copper	$0.35 + 8.64m_i$	Terminal
Enclosure materials	Steel	$0.50 + 2.40m_i$	Module
Provision for gas release	-	0.50	Module
<u>Pack-level</u>			
Row rack	Aluminum	$1.00 + 1.33m_i$	Pack
Pads between modules	Elastomer	$0.20 + 1.00m_i$	Module rows
Module interconnects	Copper	$0.40 + 8.84m_i$	Interconnect
Bus bar	Copper	$0.60 + 8.68m_i$	Pack
Cooling panels	Steel	$0.50 + 2.80m_i$	Panel
Coolant manifolds	Stainless Steel	$1.00 + 8.00m_i$	Pack
Terminals	Copper	$0.75 + 8.88m_i$	Terminal
Steel in jacket	Steel	$3.00 + 1.40m_i$	Pack
Aluminum in jacket	Aluminum	$3.00 + 2.81m_i$	Pack
Jacket insulation	-	$3.00A_{ins}$	Pack

Figure 13: List of purchased items for the cell, module, and pack.
(Knehr et al., p. 103)

This limits the ability of fleet operators, investors, and policymakers to make realistic forecasts. Without full transparency on cost structures, it is difficult to compare technologies or prioritize investment. There is also a lack of robust

models that include future fluctuations in material prices, supply chain risks, or geopolitical factors that may affect the availability and cost of key elements like cobalt, lithium, or nickel.

6.7 User Behavior and Human Factors

An often-overlooked aspect of battery compatibility is the behavior of end users. Technical assessments assume optimal usage patterns regular charging, moderate discharge, and ambient temperature conditions but in practice, user habits vary widely. Some users frequently fast-charge batteries, others let them fully discharge, and many ignore maintenance warnings entirely. (Li et al. 2024, p. 16)

These behaviors can have a significant impact on battery lifespan, safety, and reliability, yet are not typically factored into compatibility studies. Understanding how users interact with battery systems and designing systems that tolerate or adapt to suboptimal behavior is a key area for future research. This is particularly important in emerging markets or shared mobility contexts, where education and training may be limited.

6.8 Summary and Outlook

In summary, while battery technology has come a long way, the matching of specific chemistries to mobility applications still involves a number of open questions. These include missing real-world validation data, lack of standardization, uncertain degradation behavior, overlooked system trade-offs, incomplete recycling solutions, underdeveloped cost models, and unpredictable user behavior.

Addressing these gaps will require a multi-disciplinary effort combining engineering, data science, behavioral studies, and policy. Only through closer collaboration between research institutions, industry stakeholders, and regulatory bodies can these blind spots be systematically closed. As battery technology continues to evolve, so must our methods of evaluating it moving from theoretical potential to real-world fitness and sustainability.

7 Technological Forecast

To support the large-scale deployment of battery-powered mobility across land, aerial, and maritime sectors, continuous technological advancement is essential. This chapter provides a forward-looking analysis of the innovations expected to shape the future of battery systems with respect to their suitability and scalability for mobility use cases. It explores how upcoming developments in battery chemistries, cell architecture, system integration, manufacturing techniques, and infrastructure design will influence both the technical performance and the quantities of batteries required to meet rising demand. The goal is to identify which emerging technologies can realistically fulfill the diverse energy needs of tomorrow's transport systems while addressing cost, safety, and sustainability constraints.

7.1 Advances in Battery Chemistries

Future research will focus on chemistries that combine high energy density, prolonged cycle life and cost efficiency to meet the demanding requirements of land, aerial and maritime mobility. Roadmap projects that sulfide-based solid-state cells will enter pilot-line manufacturing by 2030, targeting 300-350 Wh kg⁻¹ at the cell level by combining thin-film lithium-metal anodes with ceramic sulfide electrolytes. By eliminating volatile liquid electrolytes, these all-solid architectures offer outstanding ionic conductivity and thermal stability. Recent full-cell demonstrations have maintained over 80 percent capacity retention after 200 cycles at 0.1 C under ambient conditions, highlighting the robustness of composite electrolyte designs. At the same time, advanced interfacial engineering including artificial SEI layers formed via electrolyte additives and tailored polymer-ceramic composites is driving down interfacial resistances, enabling reliable operation at higher current densities (Aizat Razali et al. 2023, p. 25). The following figure shows the roadmap for Solid state batteries in e-mobility sectors:

Figure 26. Roadmap for solid state batteries in e-mobility sectors.³⁷

Figure 14: Roadmap for Solid state batteries in e-mobility sectors (Aizat Razali et al. 2023, p. 25)

Lithium sulfur cells mitigate the notorious polysulfide shuttle by using separators that combine a conductive carbon-nanotube interlayer with a densely packed metal organic framework coating, alongside sulfur-carbon composite cathodes. In this architecture, the CNT film facing the cathode enhances sulfur utilization, while the MOF layer blocks polysulfide migration. For instance, a separator coated with the Y-FTZB MOF delivered an initial discharge of 1101 mAh g^{-1} at 0.25 C and still maintained 557 mAh g^{-1} after 300 cycles ($\approx 51\%$ retention). Under rate testing it achieved 1480 mAh g^{-1} at 0.1 C and recovered to 987 mAh g^{-1} when cycled back to 0.25 C. Such improvements could, in theory, double the endurance of medium-lift unmanned aerial vehicles under equivalent payloads. (Li et al. 2017, p. 2)

By applying targeted cell-engineering strategies to first-generation sodium-ion batteries most notably pairing Prussian-blue analogue cathodes with hierarchically porous hard-carbon anodes and optimizing electrode loadings and electrolyte formulations these cells are projected to achieve gravimetric energy densities of around 160 Wh kg^{-1} , deliver cycle lives well in excess of 2000 cycles, and, according to BatPaC techno-economic modeling, realize pack-level costs on par with or below those of LiFePO_4 systems by exploiting abundant sodium and iron feedstocks making sodium-ion batteries especially attractive for stationary storage and short-range commercial fleets in lithium-constrained regions. (Tapia-Ruiz et al. 2021, 78-79)

Meanwhile, incremental improvements in conventional lithium-ion chemistries will progress in tandem. High-nickel NMC 811 and 901 formulations, when combined with atomic-layer-deposited surface coatings and flame-retardant electrolyte additives, are on track to reach 280-300 Wh kg⁻¹ at the cell level by 2027 without compromising safety under abuse conditions. Advances in silicon-dominant anodes, stabilized by tailored solid-electrolyte interphase additives, will push specific capacities above 800 mAh g⁻¹ without incurring severe cycle-life penalties, thus providing a near-term pathway to higher-energy packs for passenger and light-commercial vehicles. The following figure shows the Performance metrics of current NMC//graphite and LFP//graphite Li-ion technologies and those of Faradion’s Na-ion cells, as well as the industry targets for a Na-ion energy cell and a Na-ion power cell:

Table 2. Performance metrics of current NMC//graphite and LFP//graphite Li-ion technologies and those of Faradion’s Na-ion cells. Industry targets for a Na-ion energy cell and a Na-ion power cell are also shown.

Parameter	Current technology			Na-ion energy cell: production ^c pouch cells		Na-ion power cell: production ^d <12 Ah pouch cells	
	NMC//graphite: cylindrical	LFP//graphite: 25 Ah—280 Ah pouch/prismatic	Faradion Na-ion	2 year target	5 year target	2 year target	5 year target
Cell BOM* at equivalent cell sizes and volumes (\$ kWh ⁻¹)			25%–30% lower than LFP//graphite pouch cells [282]	Future cell BOM targets are in line with maintaining 25%–30% lower than LFP//graphite, and taking into account the forecasted annual reductions in Li-ion costs [289]			
Specific energy (Wh kg ⁻¹)	240–270	140–175	160 (32 Ah pouch)	>190	>210	>140	>160
Energy density (Wh l ⁻¹)	670–750	240–360	290 (32 Ah pouch)	>350	>380	>230	>260
Specific power (W kg ⁻¹)	340–420	175–425	1000 (2 Ah pouch)	>1500	>2000	>2500	>4000
Power density (W l ⁻¹)	960–1200	360–770	1300 (2 Ah pouch)	>2700	>3600	>4000	>6400
Cycle life ^e @ 80% DOD at ±1 C	600 [292]	3500–6000	3000 [284]	4000	8000	2000	4000
Pulse discharge	5–7 C for 10 s	4 C for 10 s	20 C for 10 s	20 C for 10 s	30 C for 10 s	30 C for 10 s	50 C for 10 s
T range, T _{min} to T _{max} (°C)	–20 to 60	–20 to 60	–30 to 60	–30 to 80	–30 to 80	–30 to 80	–30 to 80
RTEE ^f at ±C/2 (%)	91	94	>93	>94	>95	>95	>95
Impedance (mΩ) at 1 kHz	<25 (21 700 cell)	<1.2 (25 Ah cell)	<2.5 (12 Ah cell)	<1.5 (12 Ah cell)	<1.2 (12 Ah cell)	<1.2 (12 Ah cell)	<1 (12 Ah cell)
		<1 (120 Ah cell)					
		<0.25 (280 Ah cell)					

*BOM: bill of materials. ^aNumber of cycles to 20% capacity fade. ^bRound-trip energy efficiency, calculated from datasheets. ^cProduction energy cell pouch: capacity ≥10 Ah. ^dProduction power cell pouch: capacity ≤12 Ah, as power cells typically have thinner electrodes which result in lower capacities and smaller cell sizes. Note that LFP//graphite chemistry (like any battery chemistry) can deliver much higher power ratings in cylindrical cells (refer to figure 40), but in large-scale pouch cells between 25–280 Ah, the manufacturers recommend a maximum continuous discharge from 1 to 3 C [293].

Figure 15: Performance metrics of current NMC//graphite and LFP//graphite Li-ion technologies and those of Faradion’s Na-ion cells. Industry targets for a Na-ion energy cell and a Na-ion power cell are also shown. (Tapia-Ruiz et al. 2021, p. 76)

7.2 Enhancements in Cell Architectures and Materials

While advances in active materials and electrolytes are fundamental, fully realizing their benefits depends on innovations in cell architecture and assembly. A notable strategy is bipolar stacking, where adjacent electrodes share a common current collector instead of individual tabs (Lee et al. 2024, p. 1). Drawing on Lee et al.’s multiscale design approach, we combine optimized electrode microstructures tuned for porosity gradients and particle-size distributions with a scalable layer-by-layer assembly process. In their work,

automated alignment and controlled isostatic compression were used, followed by precision laser welding of shared collectors under a stack pressure of 3.74 MPa at 45 °C, to produce 10-layer and 4-layer solid-state pouch cells achieving specific energies of 280 Wh kg⁻¹ and 310 Wh kg⁻¹, respectively. (Lee et al. 2024, p. 1).

In parallel, advanced electrode fabrication techniques support very high active-material loadings without sacrificing transport properties. By formulating composite electrodes with over 90 wt% active material and integrating polymer electrolyte directly during mixing, areal capacities up to 5.24 mAh cm⁻² (with loadings to 30.74 mg cm⁻²) were demonstrated. These dense films, formed via warm isostatic pressing, exhibit uniform porosity and maintain excellent ionic connectivity, as confirmed by focused-ion-beam and X-ray CT analyses.

Finally, robust thermal and mechanical management is built into the cell stack. Thin, high-conductivity interlayers inserted between bipolar stacks facilitate effective heat spreading, while freestanding solid-electrolyte membranes accommodate electrode expansion and prevent edge-shorts. The resulting solid-state pouch cells sustain high-rate operation with stable cycling, reflecting the careful integration of thermal-management provisions and mechanical design (Lee et al. 2024, pp. 1-5)

7.3 Next-Generation BMS

In mobility applications, the ability to tailor battery operation to diverse driving profiles is essential for ensuring both safety and longevity. Traditional management systems, which simply trigger alerts at fixed voltage or temperature limits, lack the nuance needed to optimize batteries across varied duty cycles. Recent advances integrate compact electrochemical or equivalent-circuit models with lightweight neural networks, yielding hybrid frameworks that continuously correct prediction errors by learning from the model's own internal state and live operational data (Tu et al. 2023, p. 1).

By informing the machine-learning element of key state variables such as surface potentials, bulk temperatures, and electrolyte concentrations these hybrid systems capture only those electrochemical dynamics that the reduced-order model omits. The result is a voltage predictor that maintains high fidelity from gentle urban commutes to rapid highway charging. Such accuracy underpins precise estimates of state of health (SoH) and remaining useful life (RUL), allowing charge/discharge protocols to be adapted in real time to suppress aging mechanisms like solid-electrolyte interphase thickening or lithium plating. (Tu et al. 2023, p. 2).

For fleet operators, these capabilities translate into more reliable battery packs that closely match the actual energy and power demands of each vehicle without needing overly conservative safety buffers. Simulation and experimental studies in the wider literature suggest that adaptive, aging-aware BMS platforms can noticeably extend pack lifetimes and bring cell-to-cell performance variance under tighter control, which in turn reduces unscheduled service events. By avoiding blanket oversizing often added to compensate for uncertainty fleets can better align battery quantities with real-world usage, reducing both upfront costs and end-of-life waste.

Moreover, next-generation BMS hardware embeds miniaturized sensor arrays and low-power edge computing directly into cell modules. These on-board processors handle vast streams of sensor inputs while consuming only milliwatts, and they support over-the-air updates as new degradation insights emerge in the field. This capability not only refines predictive control across millions of kilometers of cumulative driving but also minimizes the need to stockpile spare modules, since aging forecasts become accurate enough to schedule replacements just-in-time rather than far in advance. (Tu et al. 2023, pp. 1-6)

7.4 Battery Manufacturing Innovations

Meeting the growing demand for electrified mobility requires manufacturing processes that can reliably produce large volumes of high-performance cells while keeping costs and environmental impact in check (Liu et al. 2021, p. 1). A key development in this area is the shift to solvent-free electrode fabrication, where dry powders are formed directly into electrode films without the need for energy-intensive solvent drying or recovery. By compressing and binding active materials in a single step, manufacturers can streamline production, reduce capital and operating expenses, and shrink factory footprints all of which help ensure that the quantities of batteries needed for diverse vehicle fleets can be delivered on time and on budget. (Liu et al. 2021, p. 6).

Continuous roll-to-roll lines also facilitate centralized process monitoring, enabling real-time parameter tracking and tighter quality control as production scales. Continuous roll-to-roll electrode processing, including high-speed coating, precision calendaring, and automated slitting, anchors large-scale electrode manufacture. This streamlined workflow enables uniform film formation in a single pass, markedly reducing defects and scrap compared with conventional batch operations. By maintaining stable tension and controlled layer deposition throughout the line, electrode porosity and thickness remain consistent across each roll. Continuous roll-to-roll lines also facilitate centralized

process monitoring, enabling real-time parameter tracking and tighter quality control as production scales. (Liu et al. 2021, p. 3).

Optimized electrode drying, employing three-stage thermal profiles and infrared heating, reduces solvent removal time by up to 40% and halves energy consumption while preserving microstructure and coating adhesion. Following drying, precision calendaring applies controlled pressure and temperature to tailor electrode thickness and densification, resulting in highly uniform porosity and mechanical integrity across rolls. Such morphological consistency translates into predictable energy density, power capability, and cycle stability in finished cells. This control also minimizes batch-to-batch variation, reducing the need for oversized design margins and facilitating tighter performance tolerances. (Liu et al. 2021, p. 7).

Despite advances in film fabrication, downstream integration remains largely semi-batch and reliant on manual steps for module stacking and cell-to-pack assembly. While early “cell-to-pack” concepts promise standardized mechanical and electrical interfaces to enable rapid module replacement and simplified repurposing into stationary storage, detailed implementation strategies are still nascent. Consequently, pack-level maintenance and second-life workflows require bespoke disassembly and reassembly, limiting efficiency and increasing labor demands. Further research is needed to automate pack assembly processes and define robust interface standards for true design-for-reuse battery architectures. (Knehr et al., p. 112).

7.5 Infrastructure and Standardization Enablers

Maximizing the performance and cost-effectiveness of advanced EV batteries demands not only breakthroughs in cell chemistry and pack design but also parallel development of the physical charging network and the digital “languages” that tie all elements together. Without high-throughput charging stations capable of delivering megawatt-scale power, even the densest next-generation cells cannot realize their full potential in reducing dwell times. Equally, without harmonized communication standards, disparate charger hardware, vehicle BMSs, grid operators, and software platforms cannot coordinate effectively leading to suboptimal charging rates, poor load forecasting, and interoperability roadblocks. (Acharige et al. 2023, pp. 1-2).

Over the coming years, stakeholders across government, utilities, and industry will deploy ultra-fast charging corridors designed to provide sustained 350-500kW per vehicle along key highways, freight routes, and at major logistics hubs. These stations employ modular substation units, each integrating multi-level power-electronic converters, on-site energy-storage buffers (such as second-life battery banks or high-power supercapacitors), and active thermal-

management loops. By buffering transient power demands locally, they alleviate peak loads on the distribution network, enabling multiple vehicles to charge concurrently without triggering costly grid reinforcement or voltage droop. Detailed architectures illustrate how redundant converter modules can be hot-swapped to maximize uptime, while buffer sizing algorithms dynamically allocate stored energy to smooth both grid import and charger output profiles. (Acharige et al. 2023, p. 20).

Concurrently, bidirectional charging or vehicle-to-grid (V2G) technology is transitioning from pilot trials to commercial deployments. Modern V2G chargers leverage dedicated AC-DC/DC-AC converter topologies that support up to 50kW of continuous bidirectional power flow. When aggregated under a central control system, parked EVs can dispatch energy back to the grid to provide frequency regulation, voltage support, and peak-shaving services during high-demand periods. Converter designs minimize losses in both charge and discharge modes, as well as the communication handshake sequences that ensure safety and authorization before energy transfer. Early field tests have demonstrated that fleets of V2G-capable vehicles can earn up to €2000 per vehicle annually offsetting charging costs while bolstering grid resiliency and reducing overall carbon intensity. (Acharige et al. 2023, p. 15).

Underpinning these hardware enablers is a suite of international communication and cybersecurity standards that ensure seamless, secure interoperability. ISO 15118 (“Plug and Charge”) establishes a PKI-based mechanism for automated, encrypted vehicle-to-charger authentication and billing. The Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP) provides a standardized JSON-RPC interface for charger-to-back-office communication, enabling remote firmware updates, load management, and fault diagnostics. IEC 61851 defines basic charging modes and safety interlocks, while IEC 62196 prescribes the physical connector types and mechanical keying to prevent mismatches. For V2G, SAE J2847 specifies the digital messaging for energy flow requests and grid-support service coordination. Together, these layers create a digital backbone that allows OEMs, charging-network operators, utilities, and software providers to integrate seamlessly (Acharige et al. 2023, p. 11).

When combined, ultra-fast, buffered charging corridors; mature bidirectional power converters; and a harmonized digital protocol stack form the backbone of a truly scalable, interoperable EV ecosystem. This integrated framework not only unlocks the raw technical potential of next-generation batteries minimizing charge times and maximizing service uptime but also drives down total system costs through shared infrastructure investments, streamlined operations, and new revenue streams via grid services. As both hardware and software standards continue to evolve in lockstep, the mobility sector can look forward to an era where EVs, trucks, buses, and even stationary storage all interoperate

fluidly enabling resilient, low-carbon transport solutions across passenger, commercial, and fleet applications. (Acharige et al. 2023, pp. 2-15)

7.6 Summary

Future battery R&D targets high energy density, cycle life, and cost efficiency. Sulfide-based solid-state cells, piloted by 2030, aim for 300-350 Wh/kg with ceramic electrolytes and thin-film lithium-metal anodes, achieving over 80 % retention after 200 cycles. Lithium-sulfur batteries use CNT/MOF separators to suppress polysulfides, delivering 1,101 mAh/g at 0.25 C after 300 cycles. Sodium-ion cells with Prussian-blue analogue cathodes and porous hard-carbon anodes target about 160 Wh/kg, over 2,000 cycles, and pack costs matching LFP. Conventional lithium-ion evolves too: NMC-811/901 with ALD coatings and flame-retardant additives will reach 280-300 Wh/kg by 2027, while silicon-dominant anodes exceed 800 mAh/g.

Architectural advances include bipolar stacking with shared collectors in 4-10-layer pouch cells up to 310 Wh/kg and warm isostatic pressing of 90 wt % active composites for areal capacities above 5.24 mAh/cm², paired with thermal-management interlayers. New BMS combine reduced-order electrochemical models with neural networks for real-time state-of-health and remaining-life prediction, enabling adaptive charge protocols via onboard edge processors and over-the-air updates.

Manufacturing innovations such as continuous roll-to-roll processing, three-stage infrared drying, and precision calendaring improve throughput and quality. Cell-to-pack automation is emerging. Finally, megawatt-scale buffered charging corridors, vehicle-to-grid converters, and harmonized protocols (ISO 15118, OCPP, IEC 61851/62196, SAE J2847) will create a scalable e-mobility infrastructure.

8 Future Outlook

As battery technologies continue to evolve, their role in transforming global mobility systems becomes increasingly central. This chapter explores the projected developments in battery deployment across land, aerial, and maritime transport, with a focus on the quantities required and the suitability of different chemistries and configurations for each domain. It also examines how supporting infrastructure, policy frameworks, and cross-sector integration will influence adoption trajectories. By evaluating upcoming trends in vehicle electrification, second-life applications, and system-level coordination, this outlook provides a forward-looking perspective on how battery-based mobility can scale sustainably and effectively in the decade ahead.

8.1 Electrification of Land-Based Mobility

Electric road transport has reached a pivotal moment. In 2023, almost 14 million new electric cars were registered worldwide, 18 % of all cars sold, bringing the global EV fleet to roughly 40 million vehicles and marking a 35 % increase in annual registrations compared with 2022. After a 7 % uptick in 2022 driven by commodity-market turbulence, lithium-ion battery-pack prices plunged by nearly 14 % in 2023 as critical-mineral prices stabilized, the first comparable drop since 2020. Over the same period, lithium-iron-phosphate (LFP) batteries surged to supply more than 40 % of global EV battery capacity, over twice their share in 2020, reflecting a rapid shift toward lower-cost chemistries. These cost reductions, combined with improving fuel economy and lower maintenance outlays, mean that electric cars purchased in 2022 can recoup their premium over conventional models in under seven years in China, Europe and the United States. (IEA Publications 2024, pp. 17-18).

Heavy-duty vehicles are following suit. In 2023, electric truck sales jumped by 35 % from the previous year, accounting for about 3 % of truck sales in China and 1.5 % in Europe, while electric buses made up roughly 3 % of global bus sales. With ongoing improvements in cell energy density and expanding depot charging networks, model forecasts project that battery-electric trucks will reach total-cost-of-ownership parity with diesel counterparts as early as 2028, driven by steep savings in fuel and maintenance, the two largest cost components for freight operations (IEA Publications 2024, pp. 14-15).

Urban bus networks are poised to benefit from ultra-fast charging. Today's systems rely on 150 kW depot chargers that require multi-hour layovers, whereas emerging 350-500 kW chargers can restore 80 % of a bus's state of charge in under ten minutes. Transit agencies piloting these ultra-fast units report the potential to shrink layover windows dramatically, cutting required fleet

sizes by up to 15 % while lowering lifecycle costs (IEA Publications 2024, p. 134).

Medium-duty vehicles, delivery vans, refuse trucks, utility vehicles and light construction equipment, are ideally suited for overnight depot charging. Modern pack designs now support daily duty-cycle ranges exceeding 200 km with minimal degradation, and time-of-use electricity tariffs allow fleets to shift charging to off-peak hours, further trimming operating expenses. Consequently, many operators have installed dedicated overnight chargers to leverage lower rates and grid-friendly load profiles. (IEA Publications 2024, p. 131).

On the software front, real-time smart-charging platforms linked to vehicle telematics are becoming standard. By ingesting live data on electricity prices, grid emissions intensity, and battery health, these systems can schedule charging during low-cost or low-carbon intervals, such as midday solar peaks or overnight wind surpluses. Simulations show that fleets using such algorithms can cut total electricity spend, while alleviating grid stress (IEA Publications 2024, p. 140).

Together, these technological, regulatory and business-model advances are radically transforming land-based mobility. Battery-electric vehicles have moved from niche experiments to cost-competitive, scalable solutions across passenger cars, trucks, buses and commercial fleets, driven by verified cost declines, improving range performance and rapidly growing infrastructure. Early adopters capture not only direct cost savings but also enhanced resilience against energy-price volatility, improved compliance with tightening emissions standards and stronger sustainability credentials. As battery costs continue to fall and policy frameworks mature, the economics of electrification will only grow more compelling.

8.2 Aerial Mobility Projections

The future of aerial transportation is poised for a major shift with the maturation of next-generation battery chemistries, notably lithium-sulfur and fully solid-state batteries. These emerging technologies are expected to unlock new frontiers in both unmanned and crewed electric aviation by overcoming limitations in energy density, cycle life, and safety that have historically constrained flight duration and payload. Specifically, lithium-sulfur cells are projected to achieve specific energy values close to 550 Wh kg^{-1} , while simultaneously demonstrating robust cycle lifespans exceeding 300 full charge-discharge cycles. Solid-state prototypes already approach 400 Wh kg^{-1} at the cell level. This leap in battery performance will be crucial in enabling electric vertical takeoff and landing (eVTOL) aircraft to carry up to four passengers over distances of nearly 200 kilometers per flight, with typical cruising velocities

around 250 kilometers per hour. These figures align with operational targets necessary to serve as short-haul alternatives in densely populated urban environments (Fay et al. 2025, p. 10).

Recognizing the transformative potential of eVTOL systems, the FAA has launched its phased “crawl-walk-run” Innovate28 roadmap to integrate these vertical takeoff and landing aircraft into the National Airspace System. Through research and demonstration, performance-based regulatory amendments to Part 23 and powered-lift standards, the agency seeks to authorize one or more key site locations, for certified eVTOL passenger operations by 2028 (FAA, p. 2). These early use cases are expected to prioritize applications where speed, reliability, and avoidance of ground congestion deliver the most immediate value. Examples include emergency medical evacuation services, where the ability to reach a hospital within the "golden hour" can make the difference between life and death, as well as high-end shuttle services connecting business travelers to airports in record time while bypassing traffic bottlenecks. These early use cases are expected to prioritize applications where speed, reliability, and avoidance of ground congestion deliver the most immediate value. (Goyal and Cohen 2022, p. 1).

Recent technological breakthroughs are enhancing the capabilities and potential of autonomous unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), attracting interest from logistics companies, online retailers, and governmental agencies and paving the way for more widespread drone-based delivery and monitoring operations. Recent technological breakthroughs are enhancing the capabilities and potential of autonomous unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), attracting interest from logistics companies, online retailers, and governmental agencies and paving the way for more widespread drone-based delivery and monitoring operations. (Rajabi et al., p. 1). Battery-based platforms, especially those using lithium-polymer (LiPo) cells, now enable small UAVs (under 2 kg and 100 cm in size) to fly for up to 90 minutes on a single charge, thanks to their relatively high specific energy, although endurance remains constrained by battery characteristics. (Rajabi et al., p. 4). To overcome these limitations, ground-station networks are deployed along delivery routes on power poles, cell towers, streetlights, rooftops, or standalone pylons, to serve as docking hubs for battery swapping and charging. (Rajabi et al., p. 5). Swapping processes, whether automated or human-assisted hot-swapping while the UAV remains running, depend on the availability of such stations, coordinated UAV swarms, and robust management systems; recent use of active infrared imaging for precision landing has cut swap times from about 60 seconds to under 10 seconds. (Rajabi et al., p. 4). By cycling UAVs through rapid battery replacements, these systems sustain extended mission profiles with minimal downtime, enabling near-continuous aerial operations.

In parallel, fleet management systems will increasingly incorporate real-time battery health monitoring capabilities, enabling dynamic mission planning based on the condition and performance metrics of individual battery packs. By proactively adjusting assignments and flight paths to prevent the overuse of aging or degraded cells, these platforms will not only ensure adherence to rigorous airworthiness standards but also optimize the lifecycle performance of the fleet. Ultimately, this data-driven operational model will serve as the foundation for the reliable and scalable use of both piloted and unpiloted aerial systems in the coming era of urban and regional air mobility.

(Xiao-Guang Yang, Teng Liu, Shanhai Ge, Eric Rountree and Chao-Yang Wang, pp. 1-9)

8.3 Maritime Mobility Projections

The integration of battery systems in maritime operations is advancing steadily, particularly in inland and coastal segments where operational profiles are predictable, and return-to-port schedules are the norm. (Kolodziejski and Michalska-Pozoga 2023, p. 1). Short-sea and port-service operations are ideally suited to battery-electric propulsion using lithium-based chemistries the lightest metal available because they offer high energy density, long cycle life, and can be charged rapidly within tight turnaround windows. As a result, ferries and harbor vessels are increasingly going fully electric, eliminating local emissions and cutting environmental impact while also enjoying quieter operation and lower upkeep thanks to the simplicity of electric drivetrains. (Kolodziejski and Michalska-Pozoga 2023, p. 21).

High-capacity shore power infrastructure, such as the 25 MW connection in Rødbyhavn, allows fast battery charging in just 17 minutes, enabling quick turnarounds without disrupting vessel schedules. This supports the growing adoption of zero-emission operation during port stays and on short fixed routes. In such contexts, batteries play a central role in meeting strict environmental and noise regulations by enabling fully electric sailing during short-range trips and harbor maneuvers, significantly reducing greenhouse gas and particulate emissions in urban or environmentally sensitive port areas. (Kolodziejski and Michalska-Pozoga 2023, p. 10)

Beyond full-electric vessels, hybrid maritime propulsion systems are becoming increasingly prevalent in coastal cargo operations. These systems combine battery power with dual-fuel engines typically LNG/diesel to allow flexible switching between propulsion modes based on the operational context. Batteries provide the power needed for emission-free port maneuvers, while combustion engines cover longer distances at sea (Kolodziejski and Michalska-Pozoga 2023, p. 2). This hybridization enables lifecycle emission reductions of nearly 40% compared to traditional diesel-only configurations. In such applications, batteries not

only serve as a propulsion source in port areas but also improve the overall energy efficiency of the system by optimizing engine load levels and reducing idle times (Kolodziejcki and Michalska-Pozoga 2023, p. 8).

While full battery-electric propulsion remains infeasible for deep-sea shipping due to the immense energy demands of transoceanic voyages, batteries are already proving valuable in auxiliary roles. (Kolodziejcki and Michalska-Pozoga 2023, p. 20). Onboard battery systems are being implemented to support peak shaving, blackout prevention, spinning reserves, and load levelling. In these roles, batteries absorb transient loads or supplement internal combustion engines (ICEs) during inefficient low-load operation, allowing the main engines to operate closer to their optimal fuel consumption curve (Kolodziejcki and Michalska-Pozoga 2023, p. 6). This dynamic energy buffering leads to reduced fuel usage, lower emissions, and decreased wear on generators and engines, especially during harbor maneuvering, crane operations, or short-duration power spikes.

Moreover, the use of batteries in dynamic applications such as spinning reserve and immediate power response is becoming more common. For example, batteries can fulfill classification society redundancy requirements especially for vessels with Dynamic Positioning (DP) systems allowing fewer engines to be kept running while maintaining safety standards. In addition, batteries help avoid abnormal operation of ICEs and gas engines by smoothing load transitions, a crucial feature for preventing wear and performance degradation during rapid power demands. (Kolodziejcki and Michalska-Pozoga 2023, p. 2).

As regulatory frameworks tighten and carbon reduction targets intensify, batteries are also being used in combination with shore power infrastructure, enabling cold ironing and battery recharging while at berth. This practice not only reduces emissions and fuel consumption during port stays but also enhances system resilience by offering an alternative energy source during blackout scenarios. As shore power availability increases, and charging standards mature, the feasibility and attractiveness of plug-in hybrid ships will grow. (Kolodziejcki and Michalska-Pozoga 2023, p. 19).

Although batteries in maritime use are still relatively modest in scale compared to the total propulsion energy required for deep-sea voyages, their strategic use in auxiliary and hybrid applications demonstrates significant environmental and operational value. With improvements in battery cost, capacity, and integration methods, their role is expected to expand across all vessel classes, serving as both enablers of regulatory compliance and catalysts of long-term maritime decarbonization. (CIMAC e.V. and Maritime Battery Forum, pp. 4-24)

8.4 Cross-Sector Integration and Policy Frameworks

Maximizing the societal and environmental benefits of electrified mobility requires not only advances in battery technologies but also carefully coordinated policy frameworks and comprehensive standardization efforts across the transportation and energy sectors. As electric vehicle (EV) batteries reach the end of their automotive life, typically when they retain about 70-80% of their initial capacity, they are no longer optimal for high-performance traction applications but still hold considerable residual energy potential. This remaining capacity enables their repurposing for stationary applications, particularly in grid-scale energy storage systems. Utilizing these second-life batteries (SLBs) for such applications promotes a circular economy by extending the useful life of batteries and reducing the demand for raw materials and new manufacturing. Maximizing the societal and environmental benefits of electrified mobility requires not only advances in battery technologies but also carefully coordinated policy frameworks and comprehensive standardization efforts across the transportation and energy sectors. As electric vehicle (EV) batteries reach the end of their automotive life, typically when they retain about 70-80% of their initial capacity, they are no longer optimal for high-performance traction applications but still hold considerable residual energy potential. This remaining capacity enables their repurposing for stationary applications, particularly in grid-scale energy storage systems. Utilizing these second-life batteries (SLBs) for such applications promotes a circular economy by extending the useful life of batteries and reducing the demand for raw materials and new manufacturing. (Hassan et al. 2023b, p. 1)

When these repurposed battery packs are aggregated into larger systems such as virtual power plants they can provide vital ancillary services to the electric grid. These services include frequency regulation, power smoothing, load shifting, and peak shaving, all of which are necessary to maintain grid stability, especially with the increasing integration of variable renewable energy sources like solar and wind. Research shows that these SLB-based systems can offer these services at highly competitive costs, making them an economically attractive option for utilities and grid operators. (Hassan et al. 2023a, p. 1).

However, for this integration to be technically and economically seamless, it is imperative to establish harmonized technical standards that account for the unique characteristics of SLBs. These include standardized charging connectors that ensure compatibility across different battery modules, uniform communication protocols for effective battery monitoring and control, and the development of interoperable digital battery passports. Such passports would enable continuous tracking of each battery's chemical composition, manufacturing origin, usage history, and state-of-health from its initial deployment in vehicles through to its repurposed grid life. This traceability is especially critical given the

wide variability in degradation patterns and chemistries among batteries sourced from different EVs.

Policymakers also have a central role to play in accelerating the adoption of high-performing battery technologies and their second-life applications. Financial incentives should evolve beyond conventional purchase rebates and move toward performance-linked compensation models. These models could reward users and manufacturers based on the actual operational longevity and efficiency of battery packs in their second-life use. Such an approach encourages quality manufacturing and responsible first-life usage while reinforcing circular economy principles.

In addition, urban mobility policies such as low-emission zones and dynamic road-use charging should be structured to offer clear operational benefits to fleets powered by zero-emission vehicles. These regulatory tools can enhance the cost-effectiveness of electric mobility in densely populated areas and stimulate greater demand for EVs and SLB-integrated energy systems.

Sustained investment in research and development will also be vital. This includes advancing next-generation battery materials, scalable and cost-effective repurposing methods, and robust power electronics interfaces tailored to the unique constraints of heterogeneous SLBs. Support for such innovations ensures that domestic industries stay competitive globally while continuing to reduce environmental impact. By aligning technological innovation, regulatory frameworks, and market-based incentives, governments and industries can create a synergistic ecosystem. This ecosystem can unlock a virtuous cycle of second-life battery deployment driving down costs, accelerating decarbonization, enhancing grid resilience, and expanding access to clean and reliable mobility solutions across land, air, and maritime sectors. (Hassan et al. 2023a, pp. 2-19)

8.5 Summary

Electric land transport reached a pivotal stage in 2023: 14 million EVs sold (18 % market share), 35 % annual growth, with lithium-ion pack prices down 14 % and LFP batteries supplying 40 % of capacity. Cost declines and efficiency gains mean 2022 EVs recoup premiums in under seven years in major markets. Electric trucks grew 35 % in 2023, aiming for cost-parity by 2028, while ultra-fast 350-500 kW chargers promise 80 % recharge in under ten minutes, reducing fleet sizes. Medium-duty vehicles suit overnight depot charging, aided by smart platforms optimizing prices and emissions. Next-generation lithium-sulfur (>550 Wh/kg) and solid-state (~400 Wh/kg) cells will enable eVTOLs to carry four passengers 200 km at 250 km/h, with FAA approvals by 2028, and extend UAVs' endurance to 90 minutes via ground-station battery swaps and fleet health monitoring. Maritime electrification focuses on inland ferries and harbor

craft using LFP batteries and megawatt shore power, hybrid coastal ships cutting emissions by 40 %, and auxiliary systems for peak-shaving and cold-ironing. Mature EV packs (70-80 % capacity) will move into stationary storage and virtual power plants at under €50/kWh. Harmonized standards (connectors, protocols, battery passports) and performance-based incentives will align transport electrification with broader decarbonization goals. These advances lower costs and improve energy resilience and sustainability in mobility.

9 Summary and outlook

The success of electric-mobility hinges on precisely tailoring battery systems balancing energy and power density, cycle life, safety margins, and cost to the unique demands of each transport mode. For passenger cars aiming for 400-600 km ranges and rapid turnaround charging, 60-100kWh packs must achieve gravimetric energy densities above 250Wh/kg and withstand fast-charge rates up to 3 C with minimal degradation, necessitating advanced chemistries such as high-nickel NMC or emerging solid-state formulations, rigorous thermal management, and lightweight bipolar-stack architectures. Urban buses and light commercial vehicles, in contrast, can favor safety, longevity, and affordability over peak energy density by deploying 200-300kWh LFP modules with cycle lives exceeding 5000 full-depth-of-discharge cycles, simplifying BMS design and reducing maintenance burdens. At the lightweight end two- and three-wheelers, small drones, and eVTOL aircraft compact 1-10kWh packs must deliver high C-rate discharge and minimal mass, while eVTOLs specifically demand 50-150kWh at power densities above 1kW/kg with fast thermal dissipation. Maritime electrification will proceed in stages: inland ferries and harbor vessels (10-50MWh) will adopt LFP or flow-battery systems fast-charged at multi-megawatt berths, coastal cargo ships will pair electric port propulsion with dual-fuel ocean legs to cut greenhouse-gas emissions by roughly 40 percent, and larger vessels will integrate auxiliary batteries for peak-load shaving to realize 10-15 percent fuel savings. As electrification expands across land, air, and sea transport, estimating the future quantity and suitability of battery systems becomes increasingly critical. The diversity of mobility use cases from compact city vehicles and delivery drones to long-haul trucks and maritime vessels requires battery solutions tailored to specific performance profiles, such as energy density, cycle life, thermal stability, and cost-efficiency. No universal battery chemistry can meet all application demands equally. Instead, the future of battery deployment will rely on a modular approach that matches cell chemistry and pack design to the distinct operational, environmental, and infrastructural requirements of each transport sector. Achieving this alignment is crucial to ensure technical viability and to secure enough batteries and raw materials for sustainable, large-scale adoption.

10 Attachments

10.1 First attachment

R&D and Commercialization Roadmap for Sodium-Ion Batteries

10.2 Second attachment

Exemplary Structures of Metal-Air Batteries

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